

STUDYING THE CULTURE OF USING DISH WASHING GEL OF THE POPULATION

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Abstract. The article is about determining and analyzing the culture of using dishwashers of the population based on a special questionnaire. The research was carried out in the form of an anonymous questionnaire for four days using the Telegram messenger. According to the results of the survey, 313 people read the questionnaires, but more than 143 people (46%) actively answered the questionnaire's questions.

Key words: Dishwashing gel, natural products, rational use of water, human health, cleaning chemical products, environmental education

1. Introduction

Nowadays, it is impossible to imagine any kind of washing in our household without the help of cleaning agents, the most popular of which are dishwashing gels and liquids. Do we all know about the properties of these cleaning products?!

Dishwashing liquid, gel is for washing dishes [1], and its regular use has a negative effect on human health and causes the development of skin and respiratory diseases [2]. For example, antibacterial detergent contains 0.02% o-phenylphenol, which is very harmful for eyes and skin. The triclosan contained in it can be very dangerous [3].

Dishes can be washed in traditional or natural ways without detergents, because our ancestors used to do it that way. Dishes can be washed in hot water, washed with

baking soda, some dishes can be cleaned with salt, washed with ash, cleaned with vinegar, and washed using liquids and powders prepared at home [4]. A person who is not indifferent to his health does not use chemical cleaning compounds regularly.

2. Method

The study was conducted using the Telegram social network in the form of a questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of the following questions: 1. Do you use dishwashing gel in your daily life? 2. After using dishwashing gel, do you rinse the dishes with a lot of water? 3. Do you know about natural products that can replace dishwashing gel? 4. Using dishwashing gel consumes a lot of water, so can you stop using it? 5. Do you know about the negative effects of dishwashing gel on human health? Respondents answered almost all of these questions through their mobile devices.

3. Results and discussion

Below are the results of a small study conducted to check and analyze the culture of using dishwashing gel. The research was conducted in the form of a questionnaire. "Telegram" messenger was used for this purpose. The research was conducted anonymously for 3 days, consisting of 5 questions, two or three different answers, and 313 people got acquainted with the electronic questionnaire directly, of which 46% (143 people) answered the questions. 54% (170 people) of those who got acquainted with the questionnaire did not want to answer the questions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Inactive (54 %) and active (46 %) participants

According to the results of the analysis, the majority of the population (54%) did not want to answer the survey questions and showed indifference. This indicator is more than half of the weight of the participants. The result can be assessed as not positive, because many people do not want to be ecological, scientific and social activists.

The first question of the survey, that is, "Do you use dishwashing gel in your daily life?" 144 people answered the question, of which 91% answered "Yes", 5% answered "No", and 4% answered "Sometimes" (Figure 2).

Figure 2

It can be seen from the answers that most of the participants (91%) use dishwashers in their homes. Answers related to not using them are a very small indicator (5%), and the indicator of the population who sometimes uses them is 4%. From this, it can be concluded that the majority of the population uses cleaning products, which is not a positive situation. First of all, it is the negative effect on the body of cleaning agents that have been used regularly for many years, as well as the fact that the containers in which they are packed are made of compounds that are difficult to chemically change (plastic, polyethylene), and the high water consumption for washing and rinsing and other factors are evaluated.

The second question of the questionnaire, that is, «Do you clean the dishes with a lot of water after using the dishwashing gel?» 143 people answered the question,

of which 77% answered "Yes", 8% answered "No", and 15% answered "Normal" (Figure 3).

Figure 3

After using dishwashing detergents, they need to be rinsed in a large amount of water for a long time. That is why most of the participants (77%) use a lot of water. The number of those who answered "No" and "Normal" to the question is much less (8%, 15%).

The third question of the survey, that is, "Do you know about natural products that can replace dishwashing gel?" 135 people answered the question, of which 32% answered "Yes", 68% answered "No" (Figure 4).

Figure 4

The results of the third question show that most people (68%) do not know about traditional and "old" cleaning methods, which is not a positive result. There are also special home-made mixtures of natural products that can replace dishwashing detergents, but many people do not know how to prepare and use them.

The fourth question of the anonymous survey, that is, "Using dishwashing gel consumes a lot of water, so would you be able to stop using it?" 142 people answered the question, of which 36% answered "Yes", 44% answered "No", and 20% answered "Sometimes" (Figure 5).

5-diagramma

Figure 5

Analyzing the answers to the fourth question of the anonymous survey, the answers of the participants were unexpected and surprising, that is, the percentage of those who do not refuse to use these gels and detergents even if there is a lot of water waste, the largest (44%) answered the question "Yes", the weight of those who answered is in the second place (36%), the participants who answered "Sometimes" have the smallest share (20%). So, most of the participants are indifferent to water saving, which is not a positive situation.

The fifth question of the anonymous survey, that is, "Do you know about the negative effects of dishwashing gel on human health?" 149 people answered the question, of which 58% answered "Yes", 42% answered "No" (Figure 6).

6-diagramma

Figure 5

Analyzing the results of the fifth question of the survey, most of the participants (58%) are aware of the harmful side of cleaning chemical products, and a small number (42%) are those who do not.

4. Conclusion

The general conclusion is that most of the participants use chemical cleaning agents, use large amounts of water, do not use and do not know about substitutes for dishwashing detergents, do not refuse to use them despite the high consumption of water, and their negative effects on human health it became known that they know the effect.

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